

Knowledge of Substance Abuse among Adolescents

Ritesh Kumar¹, Sashikant Kumar Mehta², Mr. Nitesh Kumar³, Dr. Sapna Singh⁴

^{1,2}B.Sc. Nursing Final year student, Narayan Nursing College, GNSU, Rohtas, Bihar. India.

³Vice Principal, Head of Department of Psychiatric Nursing, Narayan Nursing College, GNSU, Rohtas, Bihar. India.

⁴Professor, Head of Department of Paediatric Nursing, Narayan Nursing College, GNSU, Rohtas, Bihar. India.

ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online 02 September 2021	Substance abuse disorder is among the leading public health problems in modern day world as they cause enormous human suffering in terms of morbidity, mortality and economic loss; and threatens the very social fabric of almost all communities around the world and such a great threat to the global health, economy and peace. The aim of study was to assess the level of knowledge and to find out the association between the knowledge of substance abuse and its consequences among adolescents with their selected demographic variables at selected colleges in Jamuhar Sasaram. The Methodology of this study was Non experimental survey approach, the target population for the study was the adolescents under the age group of 16-20 years. Total 100 samples were selected using the convenient sampling technique. Tool consists of two sections which includes socio demographic variables and self-structured knowledge questionnaire regarding substance abuse and its consequences among adolescents. Results shows that the Level of knowledge among adolescent of the age group between 16-20 years regarding substance abuse and its consequences revealed that 84% adolescents had good knowledge and 16% adolescents had average knowledge. There was Statistical significant association between the knowledge and sociodemographic variables such as types of family, family monthly income and previous knowledge of substance abuse and its consequences. There was positive correlation between level of knowledge and its consequences among adolescents ($r = 0.0583$). The study concluded that adolescents having good knowledge regarding substance abuse and its consequences.
Corresponding Author: Dr. Sapna Singh	
KEYWORDS: Substance abuse and its consequences, Adolescents, Knowledge	

INTRODUCTION

Substance abuse has become a global phenomenon. It has affected almost every country, although its extent and characteristics differ from region to region. It is estimated that at least 40 million people throughout the world are regular substance or drug abusers. The period of adolescence is a vulnerable period in the life of an individual. The increased vulnerability in this period related to psychological factors like curiosity, poor impulse control, run away from reality, psychological distress. The social factors like peer influence, lack of clear identity, and self or intra familial conflict also expose the adolescence to substance abuse. In 2015 substance use disorder resulted in 307,400 deaths, up from 165,000 deaths in 1990. Of these the highest numbers are from alcohol use disorders at 137,500 opioid use disorder at 122,100 deaths, amphetamine use disorders at 12,200 deaths, and cocaine use disorders at 11,100¹.

About 200 million people worldwide use illegal drugs each year according to new report which caused a quarter million deaths per year most seen developed countries. The majority of substance users begin the habit of using the products in their teen age life before reaching 18 years which is determined that maturity is. It is predicted that the patterns of using substance abuse that seen now continues to life time. The result leads to death of young and adult people mostly in developing countries. Teenagers in schools are also concerned with this diseased trend of using harmful drugs by their peers eventually they join in the bad habit like, smoking, drinking, alcohol.

The current estimated of deaths due to harmful substances are as follows;

In 2004, WHO suggested that 250,000 deaths worldwide was due to illicit drugs, 2.25 million due to alcohol, 5.1 million due to tobacco. The harmful use of alcohol and tobacco is a global problem which comprises individual and social development.

“Knowledge of Substance Abuse among Adolescents”

It results in 2.5million deaths each year due to physical and psychological effects to drug users, 320,000 young people aged 15-29 year. 440,000 death annually, active smokers - 269,655 death annually for men and 173,940 females annually. Passive smoking – 49,400,000 death per year.

RESEARCH STATEMENT

“A descriptive study to assess the knowledge regarding substance abuse and its consequences among adolescents at selected college in Jamuhar, Sasaram.”

OBJECTIVES

- To assess the level of knowledge regarding substance abuse and its consequences among adolescents selected colleges in Jamuhar Sasaram.
- To find out the association between the knowledge of substance abuse and its consequences among adolescents with their selected demographic variables.

OPERATIONAL DEFINITION

- **Assess:** - It refers to measure the knowledge of the adolescents regarding the substance abuse through questionnaire.
- **Knowledge:** - It is the information possessed by adolescents regarding substance abuse and its consequences using self structured questionnaire.
- **Substance abuse:** - It is the use of drugs (solid, powder, liquid or gas form) in amounts or by methods which are harmful to the individuals. Drug may be medicines, tobacco, alcohol, cocaine, marijuana, heroine, etc. Use of such drugs for the wrong purpose in a way that is harmful or morally wrong.
- **Substance abuse and its Consequences:** - it refers to physical effects, psychological effects, financial effects & social effects on person.
- **Adolescents:** - It refers to the person who's age group between 16 to 20 years.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Research Approach

Non experimental survey approach

Research Design

Descriptive research design

Variable under Study

- **Research Variables:-** The research variables under study are knowledge regarding substance abuse and its consequences.
- **Socio-Demographic Variables:-** The socio demographic variables under the study are age, gender, education, education level of father, education level of mother, occupation of father , occupation of mother, type of family, family

monthly income, living with, previous knowledge of substance abuse and its consequences , history of any use of substance abuse in family , are you taking any substance abuse.

SETTING OF THE STUDY

The study conducted among the adolescents who's age group between 16-20 years at selected college in Jamuhar , Rohtas . This colleges is located under GNSU(Gopal Narayan Singh university).

SAMPLE

The sample for the study comprised of 100 adolescents from B.Sc. Agriculture and BCA under age group of between 16-20 years study Under GNSU.

Sample Technique

Simple random sample techniques.

Sampling Criteria: -

Inclusion Criteria

1. Adolescents who's age group between 16 to 20 years.
2. Adolescents who are present at the time of study.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Adolescents who are not willing to participate in the study.

Development of the Tool

The investigator developed a structured self administered questionnaire regarding knowledge among adolescents age between 16 to 20 years regarding substance abuse and it's consequences.

Description of the Tool

The structure self administer questionnaire comprised of 2 section.

SECTION –A: Socio demographic data

The first part of the tool consisted of 13 items describing the socio demographic variables of adolescents such as age , gender, education, education of father, education of mother, occupation of father, occupation of mother , type of family, family monthly income, living with, previous knowledge of substance abuse and its consequences , history of any use of substance abuse in family , are you taking any substance abuse regarding substance abuse and its consequences.

SECTION-B: Questionnaire on knowledge regarding substance abuse and its consequences

It consists of 34 items which includes concepts of substance abuse, physical effect , psychological effects , social effects and treatment modalities . Each question has 1 correct response and 0 for incorrect responses. The total possible corrects responses are 34 giving rises to maximum score of 34.

THE LEVEL OF KNOWLEDGE SCORE IS =

Good knowledge =Score 21 to 34

Average knowledge = score 11to 20

“Knowledge of Substance Abuse among Adolescents”

Poor knowledge = score 0 to 10

DATA COLLECTION PROCEDURE

The investigator selected 100 adolescents meeting inclusion criteria for data collection using simple random sampling technique from Gopal Narayan Singh University, Rohtas, Bihar. The investigator interacted through online google meet collectively at one time and explain the purpose of the study, the cooperation required and the anonymity assured before obtaining verbal and written consent. Attempt were made to establish good rapport to gain confidence and cooperation from the subject who facilitated the data collection process. The data was collected using self structured questionnaire administered through google form. 100 samples were collected from BCA 1st year, BCA 2nd year and B.Sc. Agriculture 1st year students.

PLAN FOR DATA ANALYSIS

The data analysis was planned on the basis of objectives and hypothesis of the study. The data obtained was analysed by descriptive and inferential statistical test. The plan of data analysis was as follows: -

- Socio demographic data was analysed by using frequency and percentage.
- The assessment of knowledge of adolescents between age groups of 16 – 20 years regarding substance abuse and it's consequences were analysed in terms of percentage.
- Co-relation of knowledge analysed by KARL PEARSON'S Correlation coefficients test.

RESULT

The distribution of level of knowledge of substance abuse among adolescents shows that 84% of them had good level of knowledge, 16% of them had average level of knowledge.

Table No: - 1 Level of knowledge of adolescents regarding substance abuse and its consequences.

N=100

Level of knowledge	FREQUENCY (n)	PERCENTAGE (%)
GOOD KNOWLEDGE	85	85.0
AVERAGE KNOWLEDGE	15	15.0
POOR KNOWLEDGE	0	0

In order to determine the association between level of knowledge of substance abuse among adolescents with the selected sociodemographic variables such as types of family and family monthly income, there was statistical significant association with previous knowledge of substance abuse. There was positive correlation between level of knowledge and it's consequences among adolescents ($r = 0.0583$), and rest no association with the level of knowledge.

DISCUSSION

The finding of the study have been discussed based on objectives and with the findings of other supporting studies. The present study has revealed the overall mean knowledge score in areas of substance abuse was 40.32%. A knowledge score of less than 29% would be considered inadequate knowledge. The findings of the study are also consistent with Jose S. (1994 who conducted a study to assess the undergraduate students knowledge and attitude towards drug abuse in selected colleges of Kerala). The findings revealed majority of the students (98.33%) had inadequate knowledge the findings of the present study has revealed the mean knowledge score of boys are 41.28, while girls had a mean knowledge score of 39.46%. From this findings it is evident that boys possess more knowledge than girls.

IMPLICATIONS OF NURSING

The investigator has drawn the following implications from the study which are vital concern to the field of nursing service, nursing administration, nursing education and nursing research.

Nursing service: -

Adolescents must be tactful enough to detect the bad peer group influence at the earliest, so that they can avoid the use of the commonly abused substance abuse at present during present and in future. The emphasis must be given about the prevention of the bad habit of the substance abuse at the teenage level.

Nursing Administration: -

The nursing administrator should see that the health promotion aspect is included in teenage care. The nursing administrator should teach about

the harmful health effects of substance abuse and its ill outcome. Apart from this, nursing administrator should think of appointing college administrator to educate the adolescents and enable them to assess and prevent the bad habit of substance abuse among the college adolescents.

Nursing Education: -

Definite curriculum must emphasize on effective college teaching. This will enable the nurse to get adequate knowledge and skills to motivate for healthful habits that can mould their personality in a right way to be good future professionals.

Nursing Research: -

Nursing research should focus on complications substance abuse associated with psychiatric disorder such as depression, anxiety, mood disorders etc. and the effectiveness of educating and training teachers, students in the prevention of substance abuse among adolescents.

REFERENCES

1. *GBD 2015 Mortality and Causes of Death, Collaborators. (8 October 2016). "Global, regional, and national life expectancy, all-cause mortality, and cause-specific mortality for 249 causes of death, 1980–2015: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2015". Lancet. 388 (10053): 1459–1544. doi:10.1016/S0140-6736(16)31012-1. PMC 5388903. PMID 27733281¹.*
2. Gupta S, Singh SS, Kumar D, Kaur T, and Arora S. Prevalence, Pattern and Familial Effects of Substance Use Among the Male College Students –A North

Indian Study. *J Clin Diagn Res* 2013Aug;7(8): 1632–1636.
[\[PubMed\]²](#)
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/24086860/>

3. Mayberry ML, Espelage DL, Koenig B. Multilevel modeling of direct effects and interactions of peers, parents, school, and community influences on adolescent substance use. *J Youth Adolesc.* 2009 Sep;38(8):1038-49. doi: 10.1007/s10964-009-9425-9. Epub 2009 Jun 12.³
4. Yang MS, Yang MJ, Liu YH, Ko YC. Prevalence and related risk factors of licit and illicit substances use by adolescent students in southern Taiwan. *Public health.*1998 Sep;112(5):347-52⁴. [\[PubMed\]](#)
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/9807934/>
5. Vasumathi. An explorative study to determine the relationship between knowledge and attitude towards alcoholism among pre university students [unpublished]. Mangalore: Rajiv Gandhi university of Health Science; 2001.
6. Medrela-Kuder E. Evaluation of the level of students' knowledge about psychoactive drug. *Rocz Panstw Zakl Hig.* 2007; 58(2): 453-8.
7. Sabharwal YK. Narcotic Drugs and Psychotropic Substances. National Convention of Rights of Child; 2008 Available from: URL:
<http://ncrcindia.org/pgp/DrugAbuse.html>
8. Nieradko B, Swies Z, Milczanowska K, Sieklucka-Dziuba M. Frequency analysis of the use of addictive substances by adolescents attending secondary schools in Sanok. *Wiad Lek* 2002; 55 Suppl 1(Pt 2): 818-24